

MOVIES: NEW METHOD FOR LEARNING VOCABULARY

*N. Jo'rayeva*¹

Abstract:

Learning foreign languages is being popular among any age groups these days. This makes people feel about world and think more widely from different approaches. While learning a language, one can face to many problems like difficult grammar rules, incorrect pronunciation, thousands of words that must be learnt. To make the learning process more interesting, watching movies can be fruitful.

Key words: Methods, foreign language learning, learning styles, kinesthetic, audial, visual, learners, age groups, movies, target language.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/jye3z064>

Nowadays attitudes towards learning languages are increasing into positive side day by day. It is becoming natural to have English or Russian classes in kindergartens in our country. It is obvious that learning languages is a good thing ever, but what about the difficulties? A coin has two sides. Learning or teaching is not so easy as some people think. Many children and adults who are learning a foreign language usually have to face to some difficulties in learning new words by heart. When a student has such a problem the teacher should know what to do. According to my research done among some students, for learning new vocabulary everybody uses different methods. It is up to the learning style of a student. As we know there are three styles of learning: auditory, visual and kinesthetic. I became interested the ways of learning new words by different people and tried to identify and observe some of them. I divided the methods according to learning styles of the students. Here they are:

1. Auditory learners. This kind of learners can find easy to remember words and phrases when they tell them loud and listen carefully. There are some tips for them to learn new words effectively:

Use new words in conversations. As soon as you learn and spell new vocabulary on your own, try to read them at the end of each week. Try using your new words during the week as often as you can.

Spell the letters of the word loudly. The letters are the skeletons of the words. If you spell the letters, it will beneficial not only to remember the word but also to write it correctly.

Learn with others. Learning is easier and more fun when you do it with others! Find a group of friends who want to learn English with you. Whatever you choose to do, you will utilize a lot from learning in a team.

Use a voice recorder. This is the most useful method I have ever heard. While spelling the words record your voice. Try to listen it wherever you go and whatever you do at any time.

¹ *Jo'rayeva Nasiba G'anisher qizi, Samarqand davlat chet tillari instituti*

2. Visual learners. Visual learners are fond of picture vocabularies a lot. The reason is that they can learn fast and effectively when they see a related picture. Here are some methods for them:

Keep a list. As you find words you don't know, write them down. Make sure to keep plenty of space between words so that you can write more about the words later. It is recommended also writing down the part of speech, different version of the word and a full sentence using the word.

Make cards and stick them everywhere around. By this way you will see these words every day and don't forget. Moreover, you can stick them on various objects. If you are learning kitchen tools or equipment you can stick them on their surface.

3. Kinesthetic learner. This kind of learners usually learn new words when they touch them. Here are some beneficial tips for them:

Keep your fingers busy while studying. One way to engage a kinesthetic learner while studying is to engage your fingers in the studying. For example, trace words and rewrite sentences to learn them by heart. Typing the words and using the computer is another great way to reinforce learning through sense of touch.

Use tools such as flashcards and mnemonics. Flashcards are great study tool for kinesthetic learners. There is something about the act of writing out the cards and the act of physically flipping them over, that engages lots of different parts of the brain. Mnemonic devices, such as songs or rhymes, are also great pair with case law and your outlines.

Take breaks when studying and try to walk while learning something by heart. Kinesthetic learners often have a hard time sitting still for long periods of time. If that's you, make sure you take frequent breaks while studying. These quick study breaks will give your mind a chance to renew itself and refocus when you sit down to study again.

In conclusion, we can say without any hesitations that everyone has some abilities to learn on different ways. Watching movies with subtitles can improve your all four skills at the same time. Besides, it is better than sitting on a chair, studying various difficult grammatical rules and trying to remember new words. No matter how we achieve something, the most essential thing is the achievement itself. If we try, we can do everything that we want. The only thing required from us is to study, study and study. If you want to begin learning a foreign language, first of all, identify your learning style and then use various methods to broaden your knowledge. In this way you can reach higher levels in the foreign language as well as improving your memory.

References:

- [1]. www.enhacemyvocabulary.com
- [2]. www.learnenglishteens.com
- [3]. *Teaching outside the box*. By Lou Anne Johnson
- [4]. *The Freedom Writers' Diary Teachers' Guide*. By Erin Gruwell and The Freedom Writers.
- [5]. Abdullayev A. A. *The role of clippings in English language //International scientific conference" innovative trends in science, practice and education"*. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 145-149.
- [6]. Алишеровна мавлонова Н. *О сопоставительном изучении фразеологии на современном этапе //Scientific progress*. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 849-856.
- [7]. Мавлонова Н. *К вопросу о типологии фразеосочетаний //Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование*. – 2018. – Т. 3. – №. 3 (68). – С. 71-73.

International Conference

ADVANCED METHODS OF ENSURING QUALITY OF EDUCATION: PROBLEMS AND OPPORTUNITIES

[8]. Alisherovna M. N. *On the Comparative Study of Phraseology at the Present Stage //Central Asian journal of mathematical theory and computer sciences.* – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 4-8.

[9]. Болтакулова Г. Лингвопрагматические особенности языковых единиц в контексте употребления //Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование. – 2019. – №. 2 (71). – С. 90-95.

[10]. Boltakulova G. F. *Adverbial variants of temporal syntaxemes //Humanities and Social Sciences in Europe: Achievements and Perspectives.* – 2016. – С. 194-198.

[11]. Boltakulova G. *Temporality and its Peculiarities in the Structure of English Sentences //Scientific enquiry in the contemporary world: theoretical basics and innovative approach.* – 2016. – С. 71.

[12]. Farruxovna B. G. *Linguistic Methods in Sentence Analysis //Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices.* – 2022. – Т. 13. – С. 54-56.